

Estimating the Monetary Value of Health and Capability Well-Being Applying the Well-Being Valuation Approach

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Broader quality of life measures aiming to assess overall well-being rather than mere health effects, recently gained relevance in health technology assessment. One of those measures is the ICEpop CAPability measure for adults (ICECAP-A), developed as an operationalization of the capability well-being approach. However, to be able to use these measurements in a cost-effectiveness framework, an assessment of the monetary value for capability well-being is needed. Therefore, the aim of this analysis is to provide a first estimate of the monetary value of capability well-being gains, including a direct comparison to the monetary value of health gains.

Methods: We applied the well-being valuation approach in order to find a monetary value for the non-market goods health and capability well-being measured by the EQ5D-5L and the ICECAP-A, respectively. Subjective well-being was captured by Cantril's ladder and assumed to reflect individual utility. The latter was separately regressed on income, EQ5D-5L and ICECAP-A, allowing to calculate the willingness to pay for a QALY and a capability well-being adjusted life year through the marginal rate of substitution of these two measures and income. Data from an online survey conducted in the UK in February 2018 including 1,373 respondents aged 18 to 65 was used. To account for the possible endogeneity of income in well-being regressions, an instrumental variable approach was applied. Several robustness checks were conducted to test the impact of specific model specifications and underlying assumptions.

Results: The base-case estimate of the monetary value of 1 QALY was £ 30,786, which is similar to values found using willingness to pay experiments. One year in full capability was valued at £ 66,597. Applying sum scores instead of utility weights for EQ5D-5L and ICECAP-A produced valuations of £ 32,141 and £ 61,979. Using the Satisfaction with Life Scale instead of Cantril's ladder to assess subjective well-being generates a lower valuation of health, with a value of £ 20,988 for 1 QALY, while the value of capability well-being remained basically the same compared to the base case (£ 66,828). Not instrumenting for income lead to estimates of £ 112,336 and £ 193,305 for QALY and year in full capability, respectively. The relative value of capability well-being compared to health was consistently around two times higher throughout the conducted robustness tests.

Discussion: Our analysis provides the first estimates of the monetary value of capability well-being, also in comparison to health. Although our analysis is not without limitations, the external comparability of our estimates for health, and the relative values for health and well-being measures, generate some confidence in the validity of our approach and results. Our results furthermore highlight the importance of accounting for the endogeneity of income in well-being regressions.